

A Study on the Argentina Climate and Natural Disasters Argentina Monsoon Time Scale, Argentina National Geoscope Project Irlapatism-A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology

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ABSTRACT:

The climate of Argentina is a complex subject. Argentina has winter, spring, summer and autumn seasons. Surface and ground water resources are also available in the Argentina. Summer rains are intense and torrential rain is common. Because of its geographical characteristics, the country is exposed to natural disasters such as earth quakes, severe storms, volcanic eruptions, and climatic changes. Argentina is a country exposed to many natural disasters, it lies south of the equator making for various different weather conditions winter months consist of droughts while summer months consist of various storms and tornadoes. Due to extreme changes in climate through the year Argentina gets hit with a lot of natural disasters. Some of these natural disasters include floods, extreme temperatures, earth quakes, droughts, floods and tornados. Mining in Argentina is an important regional producer of minerals including Aluminum, lead, copper, zinc, silver and gold etc.

Keeping in view of all the above facts of climate and natural hazards of the Argentina, I have conducted many comprehensive studies on the Argentina climate and natural calamities combined with my researches and proposed the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale, and Argentina National Geoscope Project Irlapatism-A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology etc which can help to estimate the impending weather conditions and natural hazards of the country in advance to take mitigation measures and save the people, crops and other assets. For example-

By setting up the Argentina National Geoscope Project and maintain, the country can be predicted the impending earthquakes, volcanic hazards (and storm surges , tsunamis etc consequence secondary hazards due to the earthquakes occur in the womb that means underground of the sea or ocean if the country have the chances of occurring of these disasters) in advance.

By setting up the Argentina National Geoscope Project and maintain, the country can be predicted the earth's underground resources like metallic resources such as iron, gold, silver, tin, copper, nickel, aluminum, chromium etc mine sites and non-metallic resources like sand gravel, gypsum, halite, uranium, dimension stones, etc. can be found by inserting many kinds of super high remote sensing technology in the area of sensor physics, signal processing used specially image processing , electromagnetic detection technology and geophysical deep underground detectors and mineral exploration equipments , natural gas sensors etc in the underground of the Argentina through the Geoscope.

Setting up the Argentina National Geoscope Project and maintain will also be useful in emerging industries such as geothermal and geo-sequestration etc.

By establishing the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale and maintain , the country can be estimated the impending weather conditions and natural calamities like rains, floods, landslides, avalanches, blizzard, droughts, extreme winter conditions, heavy rainfall, mudflows, extreme weather, cyclones, cloud bursts, sand storms, hails, and winds etc in advance. Surface water resources in advance.

KEY WORDS: *Argentina Monsoon Time Scale, Argentina National Geoscope Project , IRLPATISM-A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology, Local Geoscope Centres, Regional Geoscope centres, Central Geoscope Centres.*

1.INTRODUCTION:

The results of researches on Argentina such as Argentina Monsoon Time Scale, Argentina National Geoscope Project ,IRLAPATISM- A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology, Local Geoscope Centres, Regional Geoscope centres, Central Geoscope Centres are very useful in studying the weather conditions and natural disasters of the Country.

2. ARGENTINA MONSOON TIME SCALE:

Monsoon means a seasonal reversing wind accompanied by its corresponding climate changes and natural hazards in precipitation. We can not be said that a monsoon especially to be relevant to a particular country. Each and every country has its own monsoon winds and climate conditions. keeping in view of all of the above geographical facts and circumstances, after study the climate conditions and natural disasters in the Argentina, I have invented the Argentina Monsoon Time scale to estimate the weather changes and natural calamities of the country.

This is very useful to invention to study and predict the Argentina weather changes and natural calamities such as monsoon wind movements, rains etc in advance. The Argentina Monsoon Time Scale – a Chronological sequence of events arranged in monsoon or weather conditions of the Argentina such as droughts, famines, cyclones, heavy rains, floods etc in the country by keen study of the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale.

2.1 USES: By development of the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale and maintain, the country can be study and predict the monsoon movements, weather changes and its related impending weather conditions and natural calamities rains, floods, landslides, avalanches, blizzard and droughts, extreme winter conditions, heavy rainfall, mudflows, extreme weather, cyclones, cloud burst, sand storms, hails, and winds etc in advance.

2.2 INTRODUCTION: The Argentina Monsoon Time Scale is a Chronological sequence of events arranged in between the time and climate of the Argentina country with the help of a scale for studying the past,

between time and weather with the help of a scale for studying the past's, present and future movements of monsoon winds in the Argentina and its relationship with rainfall and other weather changes and natural hazards of the country.

Prepare the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th of a required period comprising of a large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The main weather events if any of the Argentina have been entering on the scale as per date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale in this manner continuously, we can study the past, present and future movements of the monsoon and other weather and its weather conditions and natural calamities of the country. The Argentina Monsoon Time Scale reveals many secrets of the monsoon and weather and its relationship with rainfall & other weather problems and natural calamities of the country.. The tracking date of main path & other various paths of the monsoon winds on the graph, denotes the onset of the monsoon and weather changes, monsoon pulses or low pressure systems, cyclones and other disturbances etc. And also we can find out many more secrets of the

Scale in this manner continuously we can study the past, present and future of the Argentina climate and its relationship with weather conditions and Natural calamities.

2.6 PHYSICAL APPEARANCE : I have invented in my researches that the Argentina or monsoon or climate has a special physical appearance just as the Indian Monsoon or climate.

2.7 MEASURINGS OF THE SCALE: I have invented in my researches that the Argentina monsoon or climate having some peculiar measures just as identified in the Indian Monsoon or climate.

2.8 CONCLUSION: The world Scientist hereby requested to continue the further researches on the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale and find out the mysteries of the Argentina monsoon and climate and can make many more modifications thus bringing many

present and future movements of the climate and its relationship with rainfall and other weather conditions and weather related natural calamities. Prepare the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th (or 1st April to Next Year March 31st or according to convince) for a required period comprising of a Large time and climate of the Argentina country have been taken and framed into a square graphic Scale . The Scale may be prepared on a manual manuscript or in a computer either in a single from, or 2 , or 4 parts later the parts should be combined with pasting.

2.4 DATA REQUIRED FOR PREPARATION OF THE SCALE:The main weather events if any such as storms, hurricanes, periodical weather events etc. pertaining to the Argentina may be taken to formulating the Argentina Monsoon time Scale.

2.5 PERFORMANCE OF THE SCALE: The main weather events if any such as storms, hurricanes, periodical weather events etc. pertaining to the Argentina have been entering on the scale as per the date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the Argentina Monsoon Time and paths of low pressure systems along with the main paths of the Indian Monsoon (South-east monsoon and north-west monsoon) clearly seen in the map of the Indian monsoon it have been some cut-edged paths passing through its systematic zigzag cycles in ascending and descending orders which causes heavy rains & floods in some years and droughts & famines in another years according to their travel. For example, during 1871-1990's, the main path of the Indian Monsoon was rising over June, July, August and creating heavy rains and floods in most years. During 1900-1920's, it was raising over August, September and resulting good rainfall in more years. During 1965-2004's it was falling over September and causing low rainfall and droughts in many years. At present it is rising upwards over June, July, August, September and will be resulting heavy rains & floods in coming years during 2004-2060. The tracking date of main path & other various paths such as south-east monsoon and north-

more developments in the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale.

2.9 INDIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE (1991): For example, I have prepared the monsoon time scale for India by preparing the scale having 365 horizontal days from 1st April to next year March 31st of 128 years from 1888 to 2016 of the required period comprising of large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The monsoon pulses in the form of low pressure systems over the Indian region have been entering on the scale in stages by 1 for low, 2 for depression, 3 for storm, 4 for severe storm and 5 for severe storm with core of hurricane winds pertaining to the date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale in this manner continuously, we can study the past' present's and future's of the India Monsoon and its relationship with rainfall and other weather problems & natural calamities in India.

2.10 ANALYSIS: The India Monsoon Time Scale reveals many secrets of the Indian monsoon and its relationship with rainfall & other weather problems and natural calamities. For example, some bands, clusters continent due to direct and converging rays of the summer sun on the India Sub-Continent and develops into the monsoon trough and maintain monsoon circulation.

2.12 CONCLUSION: The world Scientist hereby requested to continue the further researches on the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale and find out the mysteries of the Argentina monsoon and climate and can make many more modifications thus bringing many more developments in the Argentina Monsoon Time Scale and make separate monsoon time scales in name of each and every Meteorological sub-divisions ,Regions of the Argentina in accordance with the weather circumstances and natural calamities .

3.ARGENTINA NATIONAL GEOSCOPE PROJECT:

keeping in view of all above facts and circumstances of geological conditions and disasters of the Argentina, I have conducted many extensive researches were conducted and invented the Argentina National Geoscope

west monsoon etc., of the Indian Monsoon denotes the onset of the monsoon, monsoon pulses or low pressure systems. And also we can find out many more secrets of the Indian monsoon such as droughts, famines, cyclones, heavy rains, floods, real images of the Indian monsoon, and onset & withdrawals of south east monsoon and north-west monsoon etc. by keen study of the Indian Monsoon Time Scale.

2.11 PRINCIPLE: This is an Astro-geophysical / Astro-meteorological phenomenon of effects of astronomical bodies and forces on the earth's geophysical atmosphere. The cause is unknown however the year to year change of movement of axis of the earth inclined at $23\frac{1}{2}$ degrees from vertical to its path around the sun does play a significant role in formation of clusters, bands & paths of the Indian Monsoon and stimulates the Indian weather. The inter-tropical convergence zone at the equator follows the movement of the sun and shifts north of the equator merges with the heat low pressure zone created by the rising heat of the sub-

into the underground and linked with the concerned analysis sections of the observatory that is above the ground to study the changes taking place in the underground That means-relative results of geological & geographical researches & developments of past, present and future should be interposed, coordinated and constantly developed. The apparatus related to the geology and geography such as Richter scale etc also should be set in the observatories of the Geoscope. we can make many more modern ideas & modifications thus bringing many more improvements & developments in the Geoscope.

And we can build many more types of Geoscopes thus connecting many more levels for national wide network, more and required geoscope centers should be established in the earthquake zones of the Argentina where earthquakes occur frequently and there should be establish a central office to co-ordinate and codify the data of warnings about the onset of earthquake. The central office should analysis the data and estimate the time, epicenter, area etc details of the impending earthquake and send to the authorities and people to take

Project to estimate the earthquakes and underground mineral and water resources of the country.

3.1. G.R.IRLAPATI'S GEOSCOPE(1980): i have conducted many researches on the earthquakes during the year of 1980-87 and invented the Geoscope which can help to forewarn the earthquakes in advance.

Geoscope means- a mechanical architecture established in between the underground and observatory with the help of bore-well proposed for conducting geological studies to know the earthquakes, underground mineral and water resources etc.

A borehole having suitable width and depth has to be dug. An observatory having research & analysis facilities has to be constructed on the borehole Apparatus & sensors to recognize the geo-physical and geo-chemical changes generated in the underground such as foreshocks, chemical changes, electrogeopulses, micro-vibrations, pressure, geomagnetic forces etc should be inserted the room lighting daily. When the bulb glows, the light in room generally appears white in color, but before occurrence of an earth-quake, the room lighting turns blue in colour. The onset of earth-quake can be guessed by this "Seismic luminescence Emission"

3.5 PRINCIPLE : Due to stress of continental plates and some other reasons on a place where there are favorable chances for earth-quake to occur, the pressure is induced in the underground. As a result, there is a steady rise in the pressure around the focus centre. Because of the large disparity in the magnitude of energies involved, gas anomalies such as (a) Helium emission (b) chemical oseismic anomalies of sulphur, calcium, nitrogen etc., chemical compounds (c) seismic atomic radiations of radioactive mineral compounds show up much earlier even at large distance from the epic-centre which enter the well through the underground springs. These gas anomalies occupy the room in this manner; emit radiation which gives blue colour (sometimes red) to the room.

3.6 MICRO-GEOSCOPE: Micro-Geoscope is an elaborate construction. For this model a

precautions.

In this system, there are three type of Geoscope models i.e Simple Geoscope Model, Home-Made Geoscope Model, Micro Geoscope Model.

3.2 SIMPLE GEOSCOPE MODEL : This is a simple construction involving no expenditure. A deep well having suitable width and depth has to be dug. Construct a room over the well. Wash the inner walls of the room with white Lime. Fix an ordinary electric bulb in the room.

3.3 HOME-MADE GEOSCOPE: This construction involves no expenditure. Even students, children's and science enthusiasts can make the Home-Made Geoscope and detect the earth-quakes 24 to 28 hrs in advance. By making certain changes and alterations, the house having a well can be converted into a Geoscope i.e., wash the inner walls of the house with white Lime. Fix ordinary electric bulbs in the room.

3.4 PERFORMANCE : Observe the colour of more changes thus bringing many more developments in the geoscope.

Observe the geophysical & geochemical changes such as foreshocks, chemical changes, ground water levels, strain in rocks, thermal anomalies, fractroluminescence's gas anomalies, electrogeopulses, micro-vibrations, pressure, geomagnetic forces, etc taking place in the underground. The onset of earthquakes can be guessed by observing the aforesaid changes in the concerned analyzing departments of the Geoscope.

3.7. ESTABLISHMENT :Geoscopes should be established at the earthquake zones of the Argentina where earthquakes occur frequently in three levels as i.e., Local Geoscope Centre, Regional Geoscope Centre and Central Geoscope Centre for maintaining the project in a coordinated manner for the entire country of the Argentina. The central office should co-ordinate, codify, analysis the data and estimate the time, epicenter, area etc details of the impending earthquake and send warnings about the onset of earthquakes to the authorities and people to take precautions.

3.8. LOCAL GEOSCOPE CENTRE : One or more required number of Geoscopes should

deep bore-well having suitable width and depth has to be dug. An observatory having the most modern high-technological research facilities has to be constructed on that well. Most modern mechanical systems like electronic, physical and chemical sensors and apparatus to recognize the rise and fall of the underground water levels, micro-vibrations and waves generated in the underground, differences in pressure, temperature and other seismic activities should be inserted into the underground and linked with the concerned research analyzing departments of the observatory that is above the well to observe the seismic changes taking place in the underground. The results of researches on the quakes like Richter scale etc., also should be setup in the Geoscope. That means relative results of past, present and future pertaining to the earthquakes or seismic researches should be interposed, co-ordinate, and constantly developed. We can make many

onset of earthquakes, the observation personal should immediately send the information to its Regional Geoscopic Centre. The Regional Geoscope Centre should analysis the information and send it to the Central Geoscope Centre. The Central Geoscope Centre analyze the information supplied by the Local Geoscopic Centers, Regional Geoscope Centers and estimates the epicenter, time, area to be affected urban places etc., details of the impending earthquake and send to the authorities, and media and warnings in advance to take precautions.

3.12. USES : This is very useful to study the Argentina underground mineral and water resources and natural calamities such as earthquakes (storm surges, tsunamis etc if the country has sea boundaries) in advance.

Geoscope can help to forewarn the earthquakes 6 to 18 hours in advance and also used to detect the mineral and, water resources of underground of the country. Storm surges, tsunamis, volcanic hazards etc geological hazard can still be predicted if the country has sea boundaries.

Earth's underground resources like metallic resources such as iron, gold, silver, tin, copper,

be established in the every expected earthquake zones of the Argentina. The observation personnel in the respective local Geoscopes should watch the onset of earthquakes day and night.

3.9 REGIONAL GEOSCOPE CENTRE :

There should be established some Regional Geoscope Centre at important earthquake regions of the Argentina to co-ordinate and codify the information supplied by the local geoscope centers of the earthquake zones of the Argentina.

3.10.CENTRAL GEOSCOPE CENTRE :

There should be established a Central Geoscope Centre to co-ordinate and codify the information supplied by the Regional Geoscope Centers from all over of the country of the Argentina in a coordinated manner.

3.11 PERFORMANCE: Whenever a Local Geoscope Centre sends warning about the the Geoscope project.

3.13 STUDIES : I have proposed many type of studies to study the earth's underground through the Geoscope. At present we discuss about two types of studies of many of them.

3.14. SEISMIC LUMINESCENCE

STUDIES : This is a very easy and simple study in the Geoscope Project. Construct a room over a well having suitable width and depth. Wash the inner walls of the room with white lime. Fix an ordinary electric bulb in the room. (Otherwise by making certain changes and alternations any home or office having a well can be converted into the Geoscope. Wash the inner walls of the house with white lime. Fix an ordinary electric bulb but don't fix fluorescent lamp in the house. This method involves no expenditure).

Observe the colour of the lightning in the Geoscope room daily 24 hours 365 days. When the bulb glows, the lightning in the room generally appears as white (reddish). But before occurrence of an earth-quake, the room lightning turns violet in colour.

Because, before occurring of an earthquake-gas anomalies such as radon, helium, hydrogen an chemico-mineral evaporations such as sulphur, calcium, nitrogen and other fracto-luminescence radiations show up earlier even at large distances from the epicenter due to stress, disturbances, shock waves and fluctuations in the underground forces. These

nickel, aluminum, chromium etc mine sites and non-metallic resources like sand gravel, gypsum, halite, uranium, dimension stones, etc. can be found. And

Geoscope is also useful In emerging industries such as geothermal and geo-sequestration etc.

Many kinds of super high remote sensing technology in the area of sensor physics, signal processing used specially image processing , electromagnetic detection technology etc should be used in the Geoscope.

Geophysical deep underground detectors and mineral exploration equipments , natural gas sensors etc should be used in the Geoscope.

Electromagnetic sensors may also be used in

- a) The light becoming weak in the violet region.
- b) The eyes having greater sensitivity to violet radiation

Due to all reasons the room may appear violet in colour then we can predict the impending earth quakes 12 hours in advance.

3.15 ELECTRO GEOPULSE STUDIES :

This is also easy study to recognize the impending earth quake. A borehole having suitable width and depth has to be dug. An earth wire or rod should be inserted into the underground by the borehole and linked with the concerned analysis section having apparatus to detect, compare measure of the electric currents of the electric circuit of the earth systems. Otherwise by observing the home electric fans.etc. We can also study the electrogeopulses studies to predict the impending earth quake.

Observe the changes in the electric currents of the earth system 24 hours, 365 days. From a power station, the electricity is distributed to the far-off places. Normally the circuit of the power supply being completed through the earth system. Whenever if the disturbances occurs in the layers of the earth's underground, the fluctuation rate will be more due to the earth quake obstructions such as pressure, faults, vibrations, water currents etc., of the earth's underground. So we can forecast

gas anomalies & fracto luminescence radiations and other chemical evaporations enter into the well through the underground springs. When these anomalies occupy the room above the well, the room lighting turns violet in colour. The light in the room scattered in the presence of these gas anomalies, fracto-luminescence radiations and other chemico-mineral evaporations the ultra violet radiation is emitted more and the room lighting turns in violet colour. Our eye catches these variations in the radiation of the lighting in the room easily since_

- a) The violet rays having smaller wave length.
- b) The violet radiation having property of extending greatly.

should be used in the Geoscope.

Geophysical deep underground detectors and mineral exploration equipments , natural gas sensors etc should be used in the Geoscope.

Electromagnetic sensors may also be used in the Geoscope project.

3.17. CONCLUSION: The world Scientist hereby requested to continue the further researches on the Argentina National Geoscope Project and make many more modifications thus bringing many more developments in the Argentina National Geoscope Project. **4. IRLPATISM-A NEW HYPOTHETICAL MODEL OF COSMOLOGY:**

There are many space disasters also cause damage to the human beings hence it is necessary to know about the universe. The cosmos is made up of universes in infinite number, having similar structure and properties, embedded one in each other and extended in ascending and descending order. To explain and justify this model, there are three universes so far known to us (a) Geo-Universe (b) Atomic-Universe (c) Energy-Universe. These three are having similar structure and properties, embedded one in each other and extended in ascending and descending order.

the impending earth quake by observing the obstruction of electric currents of circuit of the earth system in the observatory of the Geoscope and also by the obstruction sounds in the electric fans etc.

3.16 SUPER HIGH REMOTE SENSING TECHNOLOGICAL STUDIES: Geoscope is also useful In emerging industries such as geothermal and geo-sequestration etc.

Many kinds of super high remote sensing technology in the area of sensor physics, signal processing used specially image processing ,electromagnetic detection technology etc

Of these three, we known some extent about the internal structure and properties of the Geo-Universe but we do not known its external structure. We know some extent about the external structure and properties of the Energy-Universe but we do not know its internal structure. Between of these three universes, we came to know a large extent about the internal & external structure and properties of the Atomic-Universe. Hence, I have taken the similarities of internal structure & properties between the Geo-Universe & Atomic-Universe to propose that all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are having similar internal structure and properties. The similarities of external structure & properties between the Atomic Universe and Energy-Universe are taken to propose that all the universe in ascending and descending order of creation are having similar external structure and properties. And the manner in which of these three universes i.e., embedded one in each other, extended in ascending and descending order to propose that all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are embedded one in each other and extended in ascending and descending order.

4.1. SIMILAR EXTERNAL STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES : According to the model, all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are having similar external structure and properties. To justify this, I have taken many similarities between the atom and photon. For example

ATOMIC-UNIVERSE

1) The atom appearing in several forms such as Hydrogen to uranium etc., being due to the Internal structure having different atomic particles at various numbers

2) The atom exhibiting several physical and chemical Properties such as weight, colour, taste, hardness etc being due to the internal structure having different particles at various number.

ENERGY-UNIVERSE

1) The particle "Photon" related to energy appearing in several forms such as radio waves, gamma rays, violet rays etc being may be probably due to the internal structure having different particles at various numbers.

2) The particle "photon" related to energy exhibiting properties such as wave length, colour, temperature etc being may be Probably due to the internal structure having different particles at various number.

4.2 SIMILAR INTERNAL STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES : According to the model, all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are having similar internal structure and properties. To explain and justify this, I have taken many similarities between the atomic-universe and Geo-Universe.

ATOMIC-UNIVERSE

1). Various atomic particles at different sizes in several numbers are present in the atom.

2) These atomic particles having three types of charges at negative, positive and neutral states are present in the atom.

3) Positively charged protons are present in the nucleus.

4) Neutrons at neutral state are present in the Nucleus.

5). Negatively charged electrons are present at large distance of the atomic nucleus in the atom

6) Additional neutrons called isotopes are present.

7) Radiation emitting from the atom.

8) There is a property of nuclear fission is in the atom.

GEO-UNIVERSE

1) Various astronomical objects at different sizes in several numbers are present in the Geo-Universe.

2) These astronomical objects having three type of charges at positive, negative and neutral states are present in the Geo-Universe

3) Stars built by atoms having positive charged nucleus are present in centre of the Geo-Universe

4) Planets at neutral state are present in Centre of the Geo-Universe.

5) There is a concept that anti-matter cosmic bodies built by atoms having negatively charged nucleus are present at large distance of the Geo-Universe.

6) Additional planets called satellites around the planets are present.

7) Cosmic rays emitting from the Geo-Universe.

8) There is a property of super Nova is in the Geo- Universe.

4.3 DESCENDING ORDER OF atoms.

CREATION : The Geo-Universe that means the Universe seen around our earth is having magnificent structure and properties such as galaxies, stars and planets and some planets such as earth having continents, countries, oceans, trees, animals. Cyclones, human beings etc. Such Geo-Universe being built by Universes of its descending order of creation that means

some neutrons having suitable conditions exactly similar to the earth planet resembling in the Geo-Universe. Such atomic Universe being built by universes of its descending order of creation that means energy particle ‘photons’.

The Energy-Universe that means the particle “photon” related to energy present in several forms of electromagnetic radiation is also another universe having magnificent structure and properties resembling to Geo-Universe and atom. Such Energy-Universe may also being built by Universes of its descending order of creation that is not yet known to us.

Thus the descending order of creation continuous infinitely.

4.4 ASCENDING ORDER OF CREATION

: The Energy-universe that means the particle related to energy “photon” having magnificent structure and properties is being as a primary syntactic unit in the universe of its ascending order of creation that means atom. All components in the atom are built by these “photons” in infinite number. Such each and every energy particle “photon” is basis to an infinite descending order of creation.

The Atomic—Universe that means the “Atom” having magnificent structure and properties is being as a primary syntactic unit in the universe of its ascending order of creation that means in our Geo-Universe. All components in the Geo-Universe such as stars, planets etc., are built by these atoms in infinite number. Such each and every atom is basis to an infinite descending order of creation.

The Geo-Universe that means the “Universe” seen around our earth having magnificent structure and properties is being as a primary syntactic unit in the universe of its

Atomic-Universe that means the atom present in several forms from hydrogen to uranium etc is another universe having magnificent structure and properties such as electrons, protons, neutrons, etc., and continents, countries, oceans, cyclones, trees, animals, human beings may be present on

Thus the ascending order of creation continuous infinite.

4.5 COSMIC-ENVIRONMENTS : The fill of structure and characteristics in the universe of the cosmos proposed as cosmic environments. For example the fill of structure and characteristics like galaxies, stars, planets etc in the Geo-Universe proposed as Geo-Environment, the fill of structure and characteristics like proton, neutrons and electrons etc in the Atomic-Universe proposed as Atomic-Environment and the fill of structure and characteristics in the Energy-Universe that means in the photon that is not yet known proposed as Energy-Environment.

4.6 SPACE WEATHER : The fill of structure and characteristics like galaxies, Stars, Planets and their orbits and other physical forces etc that surrounds in the universe proposed as space atmosphere, the state of galaxies, stars, planets, nebulas. Pulsars etc at a particular region over a long period of time proposed as space-climate, the state of characteristics of space- climate like solar wind flares, asteroids etc at a particular region during a short period of time proposed as space-weather.

.7 SPACE REGIONS The state of space atmosphere being in still proposed as “Inactive Space Region”, the state of space atmosphere being in active proposed as “Active Space Region” The region of space atmosphere in which the celestial bodies are more widespread areas proposed as “Space High Pressure Area”, the less widespread areas proposed as “ Space Low Pressure Area”.

4.8 SPACE LOW PRESSURE SYSTEMS : Some space times, happens variation of differences of pressure in the space-climate, At such a juncture, the celestial bodies and other

ascending order of creation that is not yet known to us. All components in that Universe are built by these Geo-Universes in infinite number. Such each and every Geo-Universe in that ascending creation is basis to an infinite descending order of creation.

black-hole and the circular whirling celestial bodies & other space dust etc caused by the space low pressure area proposed as Galaxy.

space dust present in the space high pressure area will try to occupy the space low pressure area all at once. In this attempt, they will whirl around the space low pressure area. The centre of space low pressure area itself is the **4.9**

CONCLUSION : We can make many studies on the weather conditions and natural calamities of the country thus inventing many more forecasting systems and proposing mitigation measures for the welfare of people of the country Argentina.

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APPENDISES

STRUCTURE OF COSMOS

Computerised basic scale from 1888 year to 1983 year for the months of 1st June to September, 31st

